

SYNTHESIS OF CO₃O₄ NANOWIRES ON NICKEL FOAM BY A NOVEL MICROWAVE-ASSISTED TEMPLATE-FREE METHOD

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Abstract

Spinel cobalt oxide (Co₃O₄) nanowires grown on Ni foam are successfully synthesized using a novel microwave-assisted template-free method. The effect of reaction temperature, concentration of reactants, and reaction time on the morphology and crystalline structures of the prepared nanowires is studied. The present work has demonstrated that uniform Co₃O₄ nanowires with diameters of 500–580 nm and lengths of 6–8 μm can be synthesized under proper reaction condition. Moreover, the proposed microwave-assisted template-free method can significantly reduce reaction time, increase reaction efficiency, and provide better control over the geometry of the nanostructures.

1 Introduction

Cobalt oxide (Co₃O₄) has shown excellent electrochemical properties. Thus, it can be used in many applications such as heterogeneous catalysis [1] as well as in sensors [2], electronic devices [3], fuel cells [4], and advanced lithium ion battery electrode [5]. In the past few years, the synthesis and functionalization of nano-sized Co₃O₄ with different forms have attracted considerable interest. Among these different forms, the one-dimensional Co₃O₄ nanowires, which are emerging as a novel and powerful class of material, have received increasing attention owing to their homogeneous nanostructures, easy to control hierarchical organization, efficient mass transfer, and large surface area. These unique properties pose significant positive impact on the improvement of their catalytic performance. Therefore, extensive efforts have been devoted to the study of Co₃O₄ nanowires. To prepare these nanostructured materials with excellent properties, several methods have been proposed, such as template-directed synthesis method [6-7], direct oxidation method [8], and template-free method [9]. In the template-directed synthesis method [6-7], the selection of

right porous materials as templates should be adhered to because failure to do so will inevitably complicate the synthetic procedures. Moreover, the use of the templates limits the dimensions of nanowires. Variation in the dimension requirement will require a new template, increasing the complexity of the preparation procedure. Furthermore, the nanowires prepared by this method easily form undesirable aggregated structures after the removal of polymers from the templates. This lowers their catalytic performance. In the direct oxidation method [8], direct oxygenation of pure cobalt foils requires high temperatures (480–520 °C), long reaction times (10–12 h), and expensive specialized apparatus. Thus, this method is not an ideal choice for the fabrication of nanowires as well. Compared with the template-directed synthesis and direct oxidation methods, the template-free method is considerably simpler and can result in uniform nanostructures. However, the conventionally used oven heating requires long reaction time and large energy input, making the template-free method costly. Consequently, the search for a simpler and more efficient method continues as driven by the need to save on time and energy.

Recently, microwave radiation has been found to increase the rate of solution-phase reactions through the high dielectric loss of polar solvents resulting from the provided microwave energy. Based on this, the current work proposes a microwave-assisted template-free synthesis method for the preparation of Co₃O₄ nanowires on nickel (Ni) foam. Ni foam possesses good mechanical property, thermostability, and high conductivity. Thus, it can be rapidly heated to high temperature to ensure the complete reaction in a short period of time. Moreover, the relatively large surface area and pore size of Ni foam can facilitate the growth of nanowires in a large area. Hence, we selected Ni foam as the substrate for the growth of nanowires. We also investigated the effect of reaction temperature, concentration of reactants, and reaction time on the morphology and crystalline structure of

the prepared Co_3O_4 nanowires. The results demonstrate that the microwave-assisted method has the advantages of time efficiency and low energy consumption, more convenient operation, and better control of the nanostructured geometry.

2 Experimental

A microwave-assisted template-free method was utilized for the growth of self-supported Co_3O_4 nanowire arrays on Ni foam. Pretreatment of Ni foam sheets, measuring 1 cm \times 1 cm with pore density of 110 PPI and with a mass density of 320 g/m² (Artenano Company Limited, Hong Kong) consisted of the following: degreasing by immersion in acetone for 10 min; etching with dilute HCl (6.0 mol/L) for 15 min, and rinsing with distilled water. Subsequently, Ni foam was soaked in NiCl_2 (0.1 mmol/L) for 4 h, rinsed with distilled water, and dried. After the pretreatment of Ni foam, the precursor for the growth of Co_3O_4 nanowires was prepared. To explore the optimal conditions, different amounts of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and NH_4NO_3 (see Table 1) were dissolved in aqueous ammonia solution (12 wt%) and mixed homogeneously under vigorous stirring for 10 min at room temperature. The resultant mixture, together with the pretreated Ni foam, was loaded into the microwave digestion system (MDS-6, Sineo Microwave Chemical Technology Co. Ltd.), and microwave-irradiated with 600 W at 70–100 °C for 1–4 h. After the microwave-assisted thermal reaction, the prepared nanowires grown on Ni foam were dried at room temperature and calcined at 300 °C for 2 h. For comparison, the conventional hydrothermal method was also employed in the present work for the synthesis of Co_3O_4 nanostructures with oven heating. Different samples and their corresponding conditions are summarized in Table 1. The morphology of all prepared nanowire arrays was observed by a scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL JSM-5600) at 20 kV. X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were obtained on a Siemens D500 diffractometer with the step of 0.02° using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 0.1542$ nm) radiation at 40 kV and 30 mA.

3 Results and Discussions

In the proposed microwave-assisted template-free method, the reaction temperature, concentrations of reactants, and reaction time are the main parameters that influence the synthesis of nanosized Co_3O_4 . Hence, we specifically studied the effect of these parameters on the nanostructure of Co_3O_4 .

Fig. 1 shows the impact of reaction temperature on the morphology of Co_3O_4 nanostructures. The nanowires grown at 90 °C (Fig. 1b) exhibited more uniform dimensions than those grown at 70 °C and 100 °C. Furthermore, the nanowires grown at 90 °C with diameters of 500–580 nm and lengths of 6–8 μm were straight and almost perpendicular to the surface of the substrate. However, in the case of 70 °C, nanoplates, in addition to nanowires, were observed on some regions of the substrate surface. Moreover, the substrate surface was not covered completely by nanowires and nanoplates (Fig. 1a). In the samples prepared at 100 °C, plate-shaped nanoparticles appeared. Based on the morphologies of the samples achieved by synthesis at different temperatures, it was observed that reaction temperature plays a vital role in the formation of the nanomaterials. Different temperatures can result in different nanostructures. To fabricate Co_3O_4 nanowires via the microwave-assisted template-free method, an optimal temperature of 90 °C should be achieved. Therefore, in the subsequent studies on other parameters, we controlled the reaction temperature at 90 °C.

The concentration of reactants is another key parameter that affects the morphology of nanowires. Fig. 2 presents the dependence of the morphology of the nanostructures on the concentration of reactants. Transformation of the morphology of samples from nanoparticles to nanowires, and finally to microrods, was observed as the reactant concentration was varied. At low concentration (Fig. 2a), absence of nanowires was noted. Instead, nanoparticles in different forms (hexagon, cubic, and cuboid) were observed. In contrast, nanoparticles synthesized using the conventional template-free method under the same concentration (Fig. 2d) exhibited irregular shapes. Therefore, microwave heating has better control over the geometry of the final products. When concentration of reactants was doubled, the sample morphologies changed from nanoparticles to nanowires (Fig. 2b). With further increase in concentration, pyramidal microrods with diameters of 1–3 μm and lengths of 11–15 μm were formed (Fig. 2c). This indicates that low concentration of reactants failed to sustain the growth of nanowires. In contrast, high concentration caused the nanowires to grow bigger, consequently reducing the surface area. Hence, to synthesize the desired nanowire structure, the correct concentrations of reactants have to be carefully selected.

In addition to reaction temperature and concentration of reactants, reaction time is an

important factor that influences the morphology of nanowires. The influence of reaction time ranging from 1 to 4 h on the morphology of the nanowires grown on Ni foam was studied. Results are shown in Fig. 3. All selected reaction times resulted in the dense and vertical growth of uniform nanowires on the framework of the Ni foam as well as the increase in dimension values (diameter and length). Moreover, growth of several secondary nanowires from the body of the as-prepared nanowires at the reaction time of 4 h was observed. The nuclei, as induced by some high-energy sites on the nanowires, are the possible source of growth of secondary nanowires. On one hand, the secondary nanowires can benefit for the increase of surface area. On the other hand, this branch structure can reduce the pore size to resist the mass transfer from the outer surface to the inner space between the nanowires and the substrate. Considering the mass transfer and surface area, the reaction time of 3 h would be the ideal choice for the preparation of Co_3O_4 nanowires.

The current work also analyzed the crystal phase of Co_3O_4 nanowires under the conditions of sample 2 by XRD, as shown in Fig. 4. Although the background diffraction peaks of Ni foam were present, the main peaks appearing at $2\theta = 18.90^\circ$, 31.14° , 36.76° , 44.80° , 59.32° , and 65.14° were attributed to the typical diffraction peaks of spinel Co_3O_4 according to the definition of JCPDS card 42-1467. No obvious peaks corresponding to other cobalt oxides were detected, indicating the high purity of the samples. In summary, the proposed microwave-assisted template-free method significantly reduced the synthesis time and increased the reaction efficiency. With this new and simple method, uniform and well-ordered nanowires can be successfully synthesized.

4 Conclusions

Spinel Co_3O_4 nanowires grown on the Ni foam were successfully synthesized using our proposed microwave-assisted template-free method. The effect of the preparation conditions, i.e., reaction temperature, concentration of reactants, and reaction time was systematically studied. These three conditions are important in the formed morphology and size of the synthesized nanostructures. Uniform and well-ordered spinel Co_3O_4 nanowires were obtained under the following conditions: reaction temperature of 90°C , $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ concentration of 0.2 mol/L and NH_4NO_3 concentration of 0.1 mol/L, and reaction time of 3 h. The typical diameters of these synthesized nanowires were approximately

500–580 nm and the lengths were approximately 6–8 μm . Compared with conventional oven heating, microwave heating can significantly reduce reaction time and increase the reaction efficiency. These affect the crystallinity of the nanostructures.

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Fig. 1. SEM images of Co₃O₄ nanostructures synthesized at different temperatures. (a) 70 °C (sample 1), (b) 90 °C (sample 2), (c) 100 °C (sample 3)

Fig. 2. SEM images of the Co₃O₄ nanostructures synthesized with different concentrations of reactants. (a) sample 4, (b) sample 2, (c) sample 5 (d) sample 9

Fig. 3. SEM images of the Co₃O₄ nanowire arrays grown at different periods of time: (a) 1 h (sample 6), (b) 2 h (sample 7), (c) 3 h (sample 2), (d) 4 h (sample 8)

Fig. 4. XRD pattern of the Co₃O₄ nanowires (sample 2) scratched down from Ni foam substrate.

Table 1 Summary of the synthesis conditions and the corresponding sizes of Co₃O₄ nanowires

Sample	Temperature (°C)	Concentration(mol/L)			Time (h)	Co ₃ O ₄ nanowire size	
		Cobalt nitrate	Ammonium nitrate	Ammonia		Diameter (nm)	Length (μm)
1	70	0.2	0.1	6	3	/	/
2	90	0.2	0.1	6	3	500~580	6~8
3	100	0.2	0.1	6	3	/	/
4	90	0.1	0.05	3	3	/	/
5	90	0.3	0.15	9	3	1000~3000	11~15
6	90	0.2	0.1	6	1	370~450	4~5
7	90	0.2	0.1	6	2	400~550	6~8
8	90	0.2	0.1	6	4	500~580	6~8
9 (Oven)	90	0.1	0.05	3	12	/	/